

Geometric Unbiased Estimator: Some Properties

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Abstract – Concepts of geometric unbiased estimator was introduced in a recent study. Attempt has here been made on identifying some important properties/facts/results of geometric unbiased estimator. This article is based on the information on this unbiased estimator obtained in the attempt.

Keywords: Estimation, Geometric Unbiasedness Estimator, Some Properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the theory of statistical estimation, unbiasedness is regarded as a desirable quality/quality of an estimator [1, 8, 12, 13]. Originally, the concept of unbiasedness [8, 9] was explained on the basis of the mathematical expectation [2, 11, 14], specifically the arithmetic expectation, of the estimator concerned and accordingly unbiased estimator was defined [1, 12, 13]. This definition later was termed as arithmetic unbiased estimator [6]. Recently, concepts of geometric unbiased estimator [6] was introduced and defined on the basis of geometric expectation [3, 4, 5, 7]. Attempt has here been made to identify some important properties/facts/results of geometric unbiased estimator. This article is based on the information on this unbiased estimator obtained in the attempt.

2. GEOMETRIC UNBIASED ESTIMATOR

Suppose

$$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$$

is a random sample drawn from a population which follows a probability distribution having parameter θ

$$\& \quad T = T(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$$

is an estimator of θ .

T can be regarded as geometric unbiased estimator [6] of parameter θ if

$$E_G(T) = \theta$$

where $E_G(T)$ is the geometric expectation of T.

Note:

(1) Geometric unbiased estimator can exist in the case of only strictly positive valued estimator but not for any real valued estimator.

It is to be noted that the value of θ , in this case, is an unknown positive real number.

(2) Geometric expectation of a random variable can also be defined as the antilogarithm of the arithmetic expectation of its logarithm.

Accordingly, $E_G(T)$ can also be defined as the antilogarithm of the arithmetic expectation of the logarithm of T i.e.

$$E_G(T) = \text{Antilog} \{E_A(\log T)\}$$

3. ALGEBRAIC PROPERTIES OF GEOMETRIC UNBIASED IN ESTIMATOR

Property (1): There may exists more than one geometric unbiased estimator of a parameter.

Proof: Let us consider a population following the uniform discrete distribution [10] described by the probability mass function

$$P(X = x_i) = \frac{1}{K}, \quad (x_i = 1, 2, \dots, K)$$

with population geometric mean μ_G where

$$\mu_G = (\prod_{r=1}^K r)^{1/K}$$

Suppose

$$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$$

is a random sample drawn from this population.

Then

$$E_G(X_i) = (\prod_{r=1}^K r)^{1/K} = \mu_G, \text{ for each } X_i \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, k)$$

This implies each X_i is geometric unbiased estimator of parameter μ_G .

Similarly, each of

$$\bar{X}_G(2), \bar{X}_G(3), \dots, \bar{X}_G(n)$$

where

$$\bar{X}_G(r) = (\prod_{i=1}^r X_i)^{1/r}$$

is also geometric unbiased estimator of parameter μ_G

since

$$E_G\{\bar{X}_G(r)\} = E_G\left\{(\prod_{i=1}^r X_i)^{1/r}\right\} = \left\{\prod_{i=1}^r E_G(X_i)\right\}^{1/r} = \mu_G$$

Thus, Property (1) has been obtained:

Property (2): There may not exists geometric unbiased estimator of a parameter.

Proof: Let us consider a population following binomial distribution [10] having parameters R (number of trials) and p (probability of success).

Suppose

$$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$$

is a random sample drawn from this population.

For this distribution, geometric unbiased estimator of the binomial parameter p does not exist.

Thus, the following property has been obtained:

Thus, Property (2) has been obtained:

Property (3): If T is geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ then T^m is geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ^m .

Proof: Let T be a geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ .

Then

$$E_G(T) = \theta$$

By index property of geometric expectation [5],

$$E_G(T^m) = \{E_G(T)\}^m = \theta^m$$

i.e. T^m is geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ^m .

Hence, Property (3) has been obtained:

Property (4): Geometric mean of a finite number of geometric unbiased estimators of a parameter is also geometric unbiased estimator of the parameter.

Proof:

Let T & S be two geometric unbiased estimators of parameter θ .

Then

$$E_G(T) = \theta \quad \& \quad E_G(S) = \theta$$

By multiplicative property of geometric expectation [5],

$$E_G(TS) = E_G(T) E_G(S) = \theta^2$$

$$\text{i.e. } \theta = \{E_G(T) E_G(S)\}^{1/2} = \{E_G(TS)\}^{1/2} = E_G\{(TS)^{1/2}\}$$

i.e. $(TS)^{1/2}$ is geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ .

Therefore, if T & S are two geometric unbiased estimators of parameter θ then $(TS)^{1/2}$ i.e. the simple geometric mean of T & S is also geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ .

Now, let

$$T_1, T_2, \dots, T_k$$

be k geometric unbiased estimators of parameter θ .

Then

$$E_G(T_1) = \theta, E_G(T_2) = \theta, \dots, E_G(T_k) = \theta$$

By multiplicative property of geometric expectation [5],

$$E_G(T_1 \cdot T_2 \cdot \dots \cdot T_k) = E_G(T_1) \cdot E_G(T_2) \cdot \dots \cdot E_G(T_k) = \theta^k$$

$$\text{i.e. } \{E_G(T_1) \cdot E_G(T_2) \cdot \dots \cdot E_G(T_k)\}^{1/k} = \theta$$

$$\text{i.e. } \{E_G(T_1 \cdot T_2 \cdot \dots \cdot T_k) \}^{1/k} = \theta$$

then

$$(T_1 \cdot T_2 \cdot \dots \cdot T_k)^{1/k}$$

i.e. the simple geometric mean of

$$T_1, T_2, \dots, T_k$$

is geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ .

Again, let

$$T_1, T_2, \dots, T_k$$

be k geometric unbiased estimators of parameter θ

&

$$w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k$$

are k positive real numbers such that .

$$w = w_1 + w_2 + \dots + w_k$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} & E_G \left\{ (T_1^{w_1} \cdot T_2^{w_2} \cdot \dots \cdot T_k^{w_k})^{\frac{1}{w}} \right\} \\ &= \left\{ E_G (T_1^{w_1} \cdot T_2^{w_2} \cdot \dots \cdot T_k^{w_k}) \right\}^{\frac{1}{w}} \\ &= \left\{ E_G (T_1^{w_1}) \cdot E_G (T_2^{w_2}) \cdot \dots \cdot E_G (T_k^{w_k}) \right\}^{\frac{1}{w}} \\ &= (\theta^{w_1} \cdot \theta^{w_2} \cdot \dots \cdot \theta^{w_k})^{\frac{1}{w}} \\ &= \theta \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$(T_1^{w_1} \cdot T_2^{w_2} \cdot \dots \cdot T_k^{w_k})^{\frac{1}{w}}$$

where

$$w = w_1 + w_2 + \dots + w_k$$

i.e. the weighted geometric mean of

$$T_1, T_2, \dots, T_k$$

with

$$w_1, w_2, \dots, w_k$$

as the respective weights of

$$T_1, T_2, \dots, T_k$$

is geometric unbiased estimator of parameter θ .

Hence, Property (4) has been obtained:

Property (5): If S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m are geometric unbiased estimators of the respective parameters $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m$, then $(S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m)^{\frac{1}{m}}$

is geometric unbiased estimator of $(\theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m)^{\frac{1}{m}}$.

Proof: Suppose

$$S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m$$

are geometric unbiased estimators of parameters

$$\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m$$

respectively.

Then

$$E_G(S_1) = \theta_1, E_G(S_2) = \theta_2, \dots, E_G(S_m) = \theta_m$$

Now

$$E_G(S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m) = E_G(S_1) \cdot E_G(S_2) \cdot \dots \cdot E_G(S_m)$$

$$\text{i.e. } E_G(S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m) = \theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m$$

which also implies

$$E_G\{(S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m)^{\frac{1}{m}}\} = \{E_G(S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m)\}^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

$$\text{i.e. } E_G\{(S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m)^{\frac{1}{m}}\} = (\theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m)^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

Therefore,

$$S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m$$

is geometric unbiased estimator of

$$\theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m$$

and

$$(S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m)^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

is geometric unbiased estimator of

$$(\theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m)^{\frac{1}{m}}$$

Hence, Property (5) has been obtained:

Property (6): If

$$S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m, S_{m+1}, S_{m+2}, \dots, S_p$$

are geometric unbiased estimators of the respective parameters

$$\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m, \theta_{m+1}, \theta_{m+2}, \dots, \theta_p$$

then

$$\frac{S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m}{S_{m+1} \cdot S_{m+2} \cdot \dots \cdot S_p}$$

is geometric unbiased estimator of

$$\frac{\theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m}{\theta_{m+1} \cdot \theta_{m+2} \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_p}$$

Proof: In this case,

$$E_G(S_1) = \theta_1, E_G(S_2) = \theta_2, \dots, E_G(S_m) = \theta_m, E_G(S_{m+1}) = \theta_{m+1}, E_G(S_{m+2}) = \theta_{m+2}, \dots, E_G(S_p) = \theta_p$$

$$S_{m+1}S_1, S_2, \dots, S_m, S_{m+1}, S_{m+2}, \dots, S_p$$

are geometric unbiased estimators of the respective parameters

$$\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_m, \theta_{m+1}, \theta_{m+2}, \dots, \theta_p$$

respectively.

First applying the quotient property & then the multiplicative property of geometric expectation [], it is obtained that

$$E_G\left\{ \frac{S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m}{S_{m+1} \cdot S_{m+2} \cdot \dots \cdot S_p} \right\} = \frac{\theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m}{\theta_{m+1} \cdot \theta_{m+2} \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_p}$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{S_1 \cdot S_2 \cdot \dots \cdot S_m}{S_{m+1} \cdot S_{m+2} \cdot \dots \cdot S_p}$$

is geometric unbiased estimator of

$$\frac{\theta_1 \cdot \theta_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_m}{\theta_{m+1} \cdot \theta_{m+2} \cdot \dots \cdot \theta_p}$$

Thus, Property (6) is obtained:

4. CONCLUSION

Concept of geometric unbiasedness is likely to be useful and/or helpful in finding unbiased estimator of a parameter in the situation where the associated data are of ratio type or other allied types.

The properties of geometric unbiased estimator, obtained here, are likely to be useful and/or helpful in finding unbiased estimator of a function of parameter in the similar situations.

Moreover, the properties of geometric unbiased estimator are likely to be important and useful in enriching the theory of statistical estimation.

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